

E.s.r. Spectra of the Radicals Formed During the Cyclopolymerizations of Acrylic and Methacrylic Anhydrides and a Comparison with Some Related Radicals*

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Received 4 September 1972

The e.s.r. spectra of the radicals formed by the addition of acrylic anhydride and methacrylic anhydride to a reacting mixture of t-butyl hydroperoxide and sulphur dioxide are reported. Acrylic anhydride shows two sets of lines, attributed to linear and cyclic radicals respectively; related monomers (acrylic acid, ethyl acrylate, acrylonitrile) give only one set of lines, attributed to linear monomer radicals $RM\cdot$, with hfc independent of the nature of R.

Methacrylic anhydride shows three sets of lines, attributed to cyclic radicals and two linear radicals respectively; related monomers (methacrylic acid, ethyl methacrylate, methacrylonitrile) give two sets of lines, attributed to two linear monomer radicals $RM\cdot$, with hfc dependent on the nature of R ($HOSO_2$, t-Bu OSO_2).

The problem of the assignment of the spectra to the cyclic radicals is discussed.

Acrylic and methacrylic anhydrides, when polymerized by radical initiators, give polymers containing both linear and cyclic monomeric units, the proportion of the latter being higher for methacrylic anhydride than for acrylic anhydride.^{1,2} Two types of propagating radical are assumed to be present during polymerization, represented by I and II in the case of acrylic anhydride.

The e.s.r. spectra of I and II may be expected to be a doublet of triplets, but with different hyperfine coupling constants. We have now examined the spectra of the radicals

* Dedicated to Prof. Santi R. Palit on the occasion of his 60th birth anniversary.

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present in these polymerizations, using a flow system containing *t*-butyl hydroperoxide and sulphur dioxide in methanol as a source of initiating radicals R. It is known that at least two types of initiating radicals are present in this system,^{3,4,5} namely $\text{HO}\dot{\text{S}}\text{O}_2(\text{SO}_3^-)$ and $t\text{-BuO}\dot{\text{S}}\text{O}_2$, and that normally only 'monomer' radicals of the type $\text{RM}\cdot$ have time to form. In order to assess the possibility that two radicals of type I, with different R and coupling constants, may be formed, we have compared the spectra obtained for the anhydrides with those obtained for related monomers, M.

The experimental method has been described elsewhere.³ Concentrations immediately after mixing were $[t\text{-BuOOH}] = 0.1M$, $[\text{SO}_2] = 0.1M$, $[M] = 0.03\text{--}0.5M$. Reaction between the initiator components in the time between mixing and observation reduces their concentrations by a factor of approximately two.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figs. 1 and 2 show the spectra obtained with the anhydrides; Figs. 3 and 4 show the spectra obtained with the corresponding acids, Figs. 5 and 6 with the corresponding ethyl esters, and Figs. 7 and 8 with the corresponding nitriles.

Fig. 1. E.s.r. spectrum of radicals obtained from acrylic anhydride (0.03M) in the presence of *t*-butyl hydroperoxide and sulphur dioxide in methanol. *a* = main spectrum; *b* = second spectrum. Increasing monomer concentration favours *b* relative to *a*. I = residual initiator radicals.

Two points should first be noted. All spectra contain a residual line from the initiating radicals ($g = 2.0033$), which actually consists of a singlet ($\text{HO}\dot{\text{S}}\text{O}_2$) and a weaker unresolved decet ($t\text{-BuO}\dot{\text{S}}\text{O}_2$).³ Secondly, all spectra are markedly asymmetric, the high field lines being stronger than the corresponding low field lines, which are sometimes of zero intensity or even appear in emission (Fig. 4). This effect can be accounted for in terms of the radical-pair theory⁶ which explains the corresponding effect in n.m.r. spectra: so-called chemically induced dynamic nuclear polarization (CIDNP).^{7,8} In the present experiments the non-Boltzmann population of the energy levels is manifest because the lifetime of the radicals is comparable with the electron spin relaxation time (10^{-5}s).^{4,5}

Fig. 2. As in Fig. 1 but for methacrylic anhydride (0.05M). *a* = main spectrum; *b* = second spectrum; *c* = triplet of third spectrum.

Fig. 3. As in Fig. 1 but for acrylic acid (0.25M). *a* = main spectrum; P denotes polymer radical lines.

Turning now to the fine structure of the spectra we see that for acrylic acid, ethyl acrylate and acrylonitrile there is one main set of lines corresponding to a radical of structure

Fig. 4. As in Fig. 1 but for methacrylic acid (0.1M). *a* = main spectrum; *b* = triplet of second spectrum. E = emission line.

$\text{RCH}_2\dot{\text{C}}\text{HX}$. For acrylic acid there are further lines, with a larger β -coupling constant, corresponding to the known spectrum^{9,10} of the 'polymer' radicals, $\text{R}(\text{CH}_2\text{CHX})_n\text{CH}_2\dot{\text{C}}\text{HX}$.

Acrylic acid is exceptional in this respect with the present initiator system. The reason that 'polymer' radicals are not generally seen in this system is probably that the rate of generation of radicals is so high that addition of a second monomer unit to the monomer radical cannot normally compete with radical-radical reactions. In contrast to acrylic acid, ethyl acrylate and acrylonitrile, acrylic anhydride gives two sets of lines both of which may be attributed to monomer radicals. It seems likely that the two radicals are I and II, the spectrum of I being independent of whether $R = \text{HOSO}_2$ or $t\text{-BuOSO}_2$. We cannot at this stage say which spectrum is to be assigned to the cyclic radical.

Considering now the spectra of the α -methyl derivatives we see that for methacrylic acid there is one main spectrum, but some of the components of another spectrum may be

Fig. 5. As in Fig. 1 but for ethyl acrylate (0.05M). The small triplet splitting (1.4G) is from the CH_2 of the ester group.

seen at high field. Likewise the presence of two distinct $\text{RCH}_2\dot{\text{C}}(\text{CH}_3)\text{X}$ radicals may be detected for both ethyl methacrylate and methacrylonitrile. It thus appears that the

Fig. 6. As in Fig. 1 but for ethyl methacrylate (0.03M). $a \neq$ main spectrum; second spectrum of similar intensity is present but, except for one high field triplet, most of the lines are not distinctly separated from spectrum a .

introduction of the α -methyl group causes the two radicals, assumed to be $\text{HOSO}_2\text{CH}_2\dot{\text{C}}(\text{CH}_3)\text{X}$ and $t\text{-BuOSO}_2\text{CH}_2\dot{\text{C}}(\text{CH}_3)\text{X}$, to have slightly different coupling constants. This

is understandable in terms of the effect of the initiator fragment on the proportions of the conformations about the $\text{CH}_2\text{-}\dot{\text{C}}$ bond. For methacrylic anhydride it is therefore not surprising to find three distinct sets of lines, although as with the other α -methyl derivatives it is difficult to pick out more than a few lines of one of the spectra. It is thus reasonable to conclude that the three spectra correspond to two radicals of type I ($\text{R} = \text{HOSO}_2$ and $t\text{-BuOSO}_2$) and one of type II (hfce insensitive to nature of R).

Fig. 7. As in Fig. 1 but for acrylonitrile (0.05M). a = main spectrum.

We cannot yet make positive assignments of the spectra to individual radicals. From the evidence of the proportions of cyclic structures in the polymers^{1,2} it might at first sight be thought that the cyclic radical would dominate in the spectrum obtained from methacrylic anhydride. However such a conclusion is not justified, for the following reason. In the polymer the relative proportions of cyclic and linear units is governed by the relative rates of the cyclization and propagation reactions, but under our conditions (very high initiation

Fig. 8. As in Fig. 1 but for methacrylonitrile (0.4M). a = main spectrum; b = second spectrum. Three distinct nitrogen triplets (3.2G) of the b spectrum may be seen at the high field end of the spectrum; most of the other lines are obscured or too weak to be seen.

rate, comparatively low monomer concentration), the relative proportions of cyclic and linear radical are governed by the relative rates of the cyclization and termination processes. Increasing the monomer concentration will tend to reduce the concentration of primary radicals and so eliminate them from participation in termination reactions. This could lead

to a reduction in the effective termination rate constant (since fewer cross-terminations are possible) and so to a higher proportion of cyclic radicals. On this basis one may tentatively assign spectrum *b* in Fig. 1 to the cyclic acrylic anhydride radicals. Since the cyclization is known to be much faster for methacrylic anhydride radicals, then if the change of structure does not greatly change the effective termination constant, it is likely that spectrum *a* in Fig. 2 can be assigned to the cyclic methacrylic anhydride radicals.

The various coupling constants and *g*-factors are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Hyperfine coupling constants (hfcc) in gauss for the radicals formed from acrylic and methacrylic anhydrides and related compounds

Additive <i>M</i>	Type of spectrum A × B × C	Hfcc (G)*			<i>g</i> *	Notes
		A	B	C		
Acrylic anhydride	2 × 3	19.9	16.0		2.0039	Fig. 1, lines <i>a</i>
	2 × 3	19.3	15.7		2.0039	Fig. 1, lines <i>b</i>
Methacrylic anhydride	4 × 3	21.7	11.1		2.0039	Fig. 2, lines <i>a</i>
	4 × 3	22.6	11.3		2.0039	Fig. 2, lines <i>b</i>
	4 × 3 ?		11.0			Fig. 2, lines <i>c</i>
Acrylic acid	2 × 3	20.2	17.5		2.0037	Fig. 3, lines <i>a</i>
Methacrylic acid	4 × 3	22.7	12.2		2.0035	Fig. 4, lines <i>a</i>
	4 × 3 ?		12.2			Fig. 4, lines <i>b</i>
Ethyl acrylate	2 × 3 × 3	20.4	16.8	1.4	2.0038	Fig. 5, lines <i>a</i>
Ethyl methacrylate	4 × 3 × 3	22.4	12.0	1.5	2.0036	Fig. 6, lines <i>a</i>
	4 × 3 × 3 ?			1.5		Second spectrum of similar intensity
Acrylonitrile	2 × 3	20.3	14.6	3.4	2.0033	Fig. 7, lines <i>a</i>
Methacrylonitrile	4 × 3 × 3	21.2	11.2	3.2	2.0031	Fig. 8, lines <i>a</i>
	4 × 3 × 3	21.8	10.8	3.2	2.0031	Fig. 8, lines <i>b</i>

* Uncertainties : hfcc ± 0.2G or less; *g* ± 0.0002 or less.

The receipt of a Visiting Studentship from The Queen's University of Belfast is gratefully acknowledged (B.D.S.)

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